

PARTNERS

The **TERRIFIC project** aims to reform the packaging sector with bio-based solutions that enhance performance, circularity, and resource efficiency throughout the entire value chain, boosting the development of a bioeconomy model able to decouple the European development from the use of resources.

TERRIFIC flagship biobased products showcase the potential of bioeconomy to drive ecological transition, circularity, and to reach important goals in pollution prevention and decarbonization.

PROJECT **COORDINATOR**

The project is supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members. Funded by the European Union under grant agreement number 101157635.

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ROADMAP FOR REPLICATION

TERRIFIC involves the "Multi-actor Interest Group" (MIG), key stakeholders across the value chain

BIO-BASED CIRCULAR FLAGSHIP PACKAGING SOLUTIONS

Eight biobased biodegradable flagship packaging products will be developed and validated across the entire value chain, considering different end-of-life scenarios and proposing secondary value chains based on recycled biopolymer materials for non-food packaging solutions.

Laminated barrier stick pack

Food trays

Multilayer barrier flexible film packaging

Expanded thermoboxes

Injection moulding coffee capsules

Thermoformed cups

Woven tea bags

Air bubble films